

RESEARCH TITLE: FACTORS IMPACTING ADHERENCE TO WATER, SANITATION, AND HYGIENE (WASH) GUIDELINES AMONG STUDENTS AT MITANTO SECONDARY SCHOOL IN KITWE DISTRICT: INSIGHTS INTO KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES, AND PRACTICES.

BY

PRESTON MWIINGA

ABSTRACT

Access to clean drinking water, proper sanitation, and good hygiene practices significantly contribute to an individual's overall health and well-being. Inadequate access to these essentials leads to diseases like

cholera, typhoid, and dysentery. Insufficient understanding, attitude, and implementation of water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) principles play a pivotal role in propagating these diseases.

The study aimed to assess how knowledge, attitude, and behavior influenced compliance with WASH practices among students at Mitanto High School. This cross-sectional study involved all consenting and enrolled pupils at the school. Data collection utilized questionnaires and observational checklists, with analysis conducted using SPSS and Microsoft Excel.

Findings indicated a noticeable inadequacy in sanitation and hygiene practices at Mitanto Secondary School, primarily attributed to deficiencies in the facilities provided. Despite an increase in students' knowledge about WASH, the enhancement of sanitation facilities seemed neglected, evident both from our observations and the students' responses during interviews. Hence, an intervention at multiple levels is crucial, focusing on improving the infrastructure to foster better hygiene practices for the students' welfare and the overall improvement of the school environment.

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Honor and Glory be unto God Almighty, the creator of heaven and earth, the author and finisher of all things for his unchanging love and mercy throughout my Journey. May you all be blessed.

Thank you.

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ABBREVIATIONS

CBOs	Community Based Organizations
DEBs	District Education Boards
GRZ	Government Republic of Zambia
MDGs	Millennium Development Goals
MESVTEE	Ministry of Education, Science, Vocation Training and Early Education
MHM	Menstrual Hygiene Management
MSS	Mitanto Secondary School
NGOs	Non-Government Organizations
NRWSSP	National Rural Water Supply and Sanitation Program

SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SHN	School Health and Nutrition
UN	United Nations
UNICEF	United Nations International Children Emergency Funds
WASH	Water, Sanitation and Hygiene
TDRC	Tropical Diseases Research center

CHAPTER 1

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) deficiencies are primary contributors to severe diarrheal diseases such as cholera, typhoid, and dysentery, leading to significant child mortality in Sub-Saharan Africa (UNICEF, 2020; WHO, 2003). The UN's Sustainable Development Goals emphasize global access to clean WASH by 2030.

A lack of understanding and poor implementation of personal and environmental hygiene significantly impact the high prevalence of diarrheal illnesses in African school-aged children (Ebong, 1994). Educating children on fecal-oral transmission, personal hygiene, and behavioral change through education is crucial to diminish disease incidence (Aiello and Larson, 2002; Curtis and Cairncross, 2003).

Quality education necessitates proper WASH services in schools (UNICEF, 2022). WASH in Schools encompasses water supply, sanitation provisions, hygiene education, and promotion. Schools with adequate WASH facilities ensure a safe water supply for hand-washing and drinking, sufficient private and culturally appropriate toilets, and sustained hygiene promotion (Adams et al., 2009). Unfortunately, many low-income countries' schools lack these facilities, adversely affecting health and attendance (UNICEF, 2012).

Globally, school-based WASH initiatives aim to reduce disease incidence, enhance school performance, and influence household hygiene practices (Jasper, Thanh-Tam and Bartram, 2012; Joshi and Amadi, 2013). Inadequate sanitation and hygiene in schools pose severe health risks to vulnerable learners, yet improved knowledge and effective hand hygiene practices can mitigate these risks (Curtis and Cairncross, 2003; Mohammed et al., 2016).

Effective hygiene promotion in schools hinges on learners' knowledge and attitudes, necessitating a blend of education, WASH services, and suitable facilities (Shilunga et al., 2018). This study aims to evaluate the knowledge, attitude, and practices influencing compliance with water, sanitation, and hygiene among Mitanto High School students.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In Zambian schools, inadequate access to water supply, sanitation, and washing facilities detrimentally impacts students, contributing to high dropout rates, particularly among girls (UNICEF, 2022). This lack of facilities leads to prevalent waterborne diseases like diarrhea and typhoid among school children.

Despite government efforts to provide sufficient WASH facilities (UNICEF, 2022), Mitanto Secondary School faces challenges with sanitation facilities. The existing ones are of poor quality and insufficient in number. Most toilets suffer from leaks and malfunctioning cisterns. Additionally, there are only a handful of hand basins with running water, but no soap. The non-functional taps throughout the school make practicing hand hygiene difficult.

The World Health Organization recommends a pupil-toilet ratio of 1:30 for boys and 1:25 for girls (OCHA, 2014). However, Mitanto Secondary School's ratio stands at 1:94 for boys and 1:90 for girls. This leads to students resorting to alternatives like open defecation when all toilets are occupied.

The school usually falls short of the recommended 75% daily water supply (End Water Poverty, 2019), maintaining only about 68%. This results in unhygienic practices, such as leaving toilets unflushed and a lack of running water for handwashing.

The inadequate sanitation disproportionately affects female pupils, causing them to miss up to 36 school days annually, with a dropout rate of 2.71%, compared to the boys' dropout rate of 1.88% (End Water Poverty, 2019). The absence of sanitary bins and accessible running water leads to female students skipping classes.

To curb the spread of diseases stemming from poor WASH conditions, it's crucial for students to adopt proper WASH practices. This study was conducted to assess students' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding WASH compliance.

1.3 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The results obtained from this study will assist with evaluating whether more needs to be done with compliance to WASH and what changes can be made to the current WASH interventions. The findings may also provide information on recommendations for policy-makers, educators and public health officers as they plan, implement and promote their advocacy on water, sanitation and hygiene in schools.

1.4 JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

This study will enable the researcher to understand how much knowledge the pupils have and their attitudes and practices towards WASH compliance. This information will help understand there is need for more improvement so that more interventions further prevent WASH related diseases.

1.5 OBJECTIVES

1.5.1 GENERAL OBJECTIVE

To determine the knowledge, attitudes and practices that influence compliance to Water, Sanitation and hygiene (WASH) standards among the pupils at Mitanto Secondary school.

1.5.2 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. To determine the knowledge of pupils to water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) compliance at Mitanto Secondary School.
2. To find out the attitude of pupils to water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) compliance at Mitanto Secondary School.
3. To examine the practices of pupils to water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) compliance at Mitanto Secondary School.

1.6 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What knowledge do the pupils have towards Water, Sanitation and hygiene compliance at Mitanto Secondary School?
2. What is the attitude of pupils toward water, sanitation and hygiene at Mitanto Secondary School?
3. How is the response to practices influencing compliance to WASH standards among the pupils at Mitanto Secondary School?

1.7 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the relationship between the dependent variable and independent variables.

CHAPTER 2

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Access to water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) in educational settings brings many tangible benefits: safe drinking-water supply and promotion of regular hydration contribute to better cognitive performance; good hand hygiene in schools reduces the risk of infectious diseases and, by keeping children healthy, reduces absenteeism; and providing accessible and acceptable toilets contributes to well-being and increases the ability to concentrate during classes. Schools that strive to provide a safe, inclusive and equitable learning environment for all have provisions for menstrual hygiene management and facilities accessible for children living with limited mobility or vision (WHO, 2019)

2.1 GLOBAL REVIEW

WASH in schools in the pan-European region presents many and diverse challenges, most frequently related to inappropriate system operation; problems with physical infrastructure; lack of continuous provision of hygiene consumables; inadequate cleaning; and insufficient maintenance. Recent evidence also highlights how WASH services in schools needs to go beyond a basic (minimum) level and meet users' needs if health gains are to be achieved. Pupils' perception surveys reveal frequent dissatisfaction with school WASH facilities, which are not always acknowledged by school management and staff, fostering avoidance of the services and hindering healthy behaviours, as well as possibly facilitating antisocial behaviour in the facilities (Grossi et al, 2016).

According to Berhe et al (2020), "Lack of knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) on WASH is one of the most imperative causes for transmission of infectious diseases. Effectiveness of WASH depends not only on the provision of WASH facilities but also, and most importantly, on the compliance of individuals. Unless people have adequate KAP in relation to WASH, mere access to the services is not sufficient to mitigate health problems related to unsafe water, poor sanitation,

and hygiene. The extent of safe WASH practices can be determined by the people's knowledge and attitudes towards WASH'.

In line with of practices of WASH a research was conducted in Bangladesh public university, were a researcher stated that, "The students are aware of the importance of good hygiene habits. But often, they fail to maintain it mostly because of the supply side. You rarely see any handwashing material readily available in the washrooms. How can a student maintain good handwashing practices after using the toilet?" (A male student in an FGD) Kabir et al. (2021)."

2.2 LOCAL REVIEW

USAID (2010) affirms that more than 25% of basic schools in Zambia do not have access to safe water supply (borehole-piped, borehole-pump, piped water and protected well), and of the 9,564 sanitary facilities (flush toilets and latrines) in schools, 87.5% consist of pit latrines and the rest are flush toilets. Pit latrines range from high quality to makeshift latrines consisting of stick and mud floors over pits of uncertain depth with flimsy enclosures made of sticks and grass and brick enclosures in most of the rural schools. These are reinforced with concrete slabs over the pits but lack ventilation and deep foundations to the bottom. There is almost equal number of sanitary facilities for both boys and girls. The ratio of pupils per toilet is generally high, reaching 90 pupils per toilet in some of the schools which is way beyond the MESVTEE standards of 1:40 for boys and 1:25 for girls (AusAID, 2012).

Hand washing facilities are also few even in schools that have been built recently (USAID 2010). MESVTEE construction plans had no sanitary facilities rendering that the Ministry would have to revisit the same schools to add this component. The general water and sanitation situation in schools does not meet the Public Health Regulations and Requirements for School toilets. This is also supported by UNICEF (2010) which affirms that there is an imbalance between the number of pupils and water and sanitation facilities in schools. It is indicative of the reduced spending on infrastructure over time, a lack of maintenance of existing structures and the bias in infrastructure development towards classroom construction over water and sanitation facilities in response to huge numbers of learners still out of school. This is coupled with the unclear policy and institutional arrangements in the provision of water particularly in rural schools. As such UNICEF

concluded in 2010 that only 37% of schools have permanent latrines, and seven (7%) have none at all. While only 20% of schools meet the accepted pupil- latrine ratio of 1 to 40 boys and 9% for the required 1 to 25 for girls.

2.3 REDUCED DIARRHEA AND OTHER WASH-RELATED DISEASES IN SCHOOL STUDENTS

Despite the biological plausibility that improvements in school WASH conditions will be beneficial for pupil health, results from school-based WASH evaluations have been mixed. There is evidence that WASH in Schools programs have a positive impact on child health, including reductions in diarrheal disease and other hygiene-related diseases. Migele et.al., (2007) examined the impact of a simple school-based water treatment and hand-washing intervention in a boarding school in Kenya: i.e., clay pots modified with narrow mouths and ceramic lids, taps for drinking water, plastic tanks with taps for hand washing, Water Guard (i.e., sodium hypochlorite solution) for drinking water, and soap for hand washing. Before-and-after rates of diarrhea disease (with no control schools) indicated a more than 50% reduction in recorded cases of diarrhea among students. In their evaluation of Wins interventions in Mali (Trinies et al., 2016) found that, as compared with control schools, there were lower odds of students in beneficiary schools reporting diarrhea or respiratory infection symptoms in the past week. And a study in rural Kenya (Patel et al., 2012) found that school-based water treatment and hygiene programs resulted in a decrease in rates of acute respiratory illness, although no decrease in acute diarrhea was observed. Improving school-based WASH can also reduce other hygiene-related diseases, such as soil-transmitted helminth (STH) infection (Freeman et al., 2012; Freeman et al., 2014). For example, Bieri et al (2013) found that among Chinese school-children, the incidence of infection with STHs was 50% lower in the intervention group that received a STH education package than in the control group (4.1% vs. 8.4%, $p < 0.001$). And in Freeman et.al. (2014) found that provision of school-based sanitation, water quality, and hygiene improvements reduced reinfection of some STHs after school-based deworming, but the magnitude of the effects were helminth species-specific.

Results, however, are not uniformly clear or positive. In an evaluation of a hand-washing promotion program in Chinese primary schools, rates of diarrhea were too low in both intervention and control groups to identify attributable differences in prevalence (Bowmen et al., 2007).

Some studies indicated that basic interventions that include hygiene promotion, water treatment, and behavior change did not reduce rates of diarrheal disease (Patel et al., 2012). In a multi-country study, Dujister et al., (2017) found that the STH prevalence at baseline and at follow-up did not significantly differ between intervention schools (that provided deworming and improved handwashing) and control schools. And a study by Greene et al (2012), conducted in schools in western Kenya found that hygiene promotion and water treatment did not reduce risk of *Escherichia coli* presence on pupils' hands; further, the addition of new latrines to intervention schools significantly increased *E. coli* presence among girls which they attributed to an absence of sufficient hygiene behavior change, and lack of soap, water, and anal cleansing materials. It is important to note, however, that presence of *E. coli* on hands is a variable that is difficult to interpret in terms of disease risk and outcomes.

2.4 SUMMARY

Overall, this chapter has provided a review of literature related to the study. The background, history and development of School WASH program have been acknowledged. Relevant literature on designing effective implementation process of the program, importance of the program and collaboration and challenges have been acknowledged.

CHAPTER 3

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology that followed in this investigation is outlined in this section. The study type, variables, study locations, and study population are all discussed, as well as the sampling method and sample size, data collecting plan, data collection technique and tools, data collection and quality control, data processing and analysis, ethical consideration, and pre-testing.

3.1 STUDY AREA

This study was conducted at Mitanto High School in Kitwe District.

3.2 STUDY DESIGN

This study employed a cross-sectional study. This is because we ascertained the knowledge, attitudes and practices among the study participants and it also allowed the comparison of different variables at the same time.

3.3 STUDY POPULATION

The study population is all 1654 pupils of Mitanto High School who are made up of 752 male pupils and 902 female pupils.

3.4 SAMPLE SIZE CALCULATION

The study population is 1654.

To determine sample size, Slovin's formula (Slovin, 1960) was applied:

$$n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$$

Where N is the population size and e is the margin of error.

$$n = 1654 / ((1 + 1654(0.05)^2)$$

$$n = 1654 / (1+4.135)$$

n = 1654 / (5.135)

n = 322.1

323 participants.

3.5 SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

The study utilized simple random sampling to select participants in the study. This method was used because it is fast and all the participants have equal chances of participating in the study and it reduced the possibility of being biased as the researcher.

3.5.1 Inclusion criteria

All pupils who consent to participate.

Pupils currently enrolled at Mitanto High School.

3.5.2 Exclusion criteria

Pupils who do not consent to participate.

3.6 DATA COLLECTION METHOD

The study used a questionnaire and structured observational checklist to collect data.

The questionnaire laid down questions that helped the researcher and research assistants to obtain the necessary data.

The observational checklist was used to monitor if pupils comply to WASH regulations and if the necessary WASH hardware such as toilets, wash hand basin and soap are in place and properly working.

After each day's activities, the principal investigator went through the filled in questionnaires to check for accuracy and completeness.

3.7 DATA PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS

Completeness and internal consistency of the data collected was evaluated. The procedure entail data categorization, coding, and data entry on a computer utilizing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

3.8 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Ethical approval to carry out this research was sought from the Tropical Diseases Research Center (TDRC) Research Ethics Committee in Ndola.

Permission to undertake the study at Mitanto High School was obtained from the District Education Board (DEBs) and school's management.

Individuals who participate in this study were provided with informed consent forms and they will remain anonymous as their information will be kept private and confidential.

CHAPTER FOUR

4. 1 DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION OF FINDINGS

Introduction

In this chapter will discuss the analysis and presentations of the finding which the respondents from the sample size of (n=323) and only (n=240) pupils of Mitanto high School responded to the questionnaire.

SECTION A: demographical Characteristics

Table 1 : Demographical presentation of respondents at Mitanto Secondary School.

VARIABLES	CATEGORY	N (%)
GENDER	Male	104 (43.3%)
	Female	136 (56.7%)
AGE (YEARS)	11-13	53 (22.1%)
	14-16	98 (40.8%)
	17 and above	89 (37.1%)
GRADE OF PUPIL	8-9	70 (29.2%)
	10-11	106 (44.2%)
	12	64 (26.7%)

Table 2 : Knowledge of pupils on WASH Mitanto Secondary school.

Do you have knowledge on the importance of WASH in School ?		
Yes	170	70.8
No	70	29.2
Total	240	100%
Can WASH prevent you from contracting diseases?		
Yes	174	72.5
No	66	27.5
Total	240	100%
Where do you normally receive information on water, sanitation and hygiene		
a. Poster and handbills	44	18.3%
b. Health education by community health workers	57	23.8%
c. Health education by teachers	49	20.4%
d. Health education by school administration	28	11.7%
e. Health education by Sanitation Action group in School	29	12.1%
f. None of the above	33	13.8%
Total	240	100 %

1. Does the school curriculum include education on hygiene?

Yes	178	74.2
No	62	25.8
Total	240	100%

1. What do you think is the harm or danger of not treating water to drink or not storing drinking water safely?

a) Diarrhea	86
b) Cholera	71
c) Typhoid	25
d) Acute respiratory infection	15
e) Water will be contaminated	29
f) Sickness (unspecified)	14

Table 3: The attitude among pupils of Mitanto Secondary School towards WASH.

Characteristic	Respondent (n)	(%)
Who is responsible of cleaning the toilet?		
a) Pupils	15	6.3%
b) Teachers	15	6.3%
c) Caretakers	186	77.5%
d) All of the above	24	10%
How often do you participate in WASH activities?		
a. Often	94	39.2%
b. Fairly often	80	33.3%
c. Not	66	27.5%
Who is responsible for personal hygiene of the pupils at your school?		
a. Pupils	126	52.5%
b. Teachers	52	21.7%
c. School administration	62	25.8%

Do you wash hands with soap after toilet use?		
Yes	124	51.7%
No	116	48.3%
Do you think diarrheal diseases are caused by poor hygiene?		
Yes	190	79.2%
No	50	20.8%

Table 4: Shows response to practices that influence compliance to WASH standards among the pupils at Mitanto Secondary School.

Variables	Category	Frequency (n=240)	Percentages (%)
a) When do you wash hands?	a) After visiting the toilet	109	45.4%
	b) Before prepring food	67	27.9%
	c) Before eating	64	26.7%
b) How does the school administration support in implementation of the activities?	a) Providing money	16	6.7%
	b) Providing materials	102	42.5%
	c) Allocating time for activities	34	14.2%
	d) Monitoring	88	36.7%
c) What is the medium of washing hands?	a) Water only	156	65%
	b) Water and soap		

	c) Water and ash	84	35%
		0	
d) What WASH activities do you have at your school?	a) Hand wash maintenance	58	24.2%
	b) Maintenance of latrines	42	17.5%
	c) Hygiene education	64	26.7%
	d) Environmental education	64	26.7%
	e) Provision of safe drinking water	35	14.6%
	f) Others (kindly explain)	41	17.2%

OBSERVATION CHECKLIST

Table 5: Shows what was observed by the researcher following the questionnaire

Questions	Response
How many toilets or pit latrines does the school have for girls?	10 toilets
How many toilets or pit latrines does the school have for boys?	8 toilets
Does the school provide hand washing facilities at every entrance/exit of the toilet and eating places?	No
How adequate is the compliance levels to WASH program at your school?	Inadequate
Is soap available at all handwashing stations?	No
Is there a backup water tank?	Yes

Are waste disposal bins available?	No
What is the condition of the toilets?	Not working well
How often is water available?	Not often

From Table 5 see here that during this observation checklist the researcher observed that the school consist of 8 toilets for boys, 10 toilets for girls, the school does not provide hand washing facilities at the entrance/exit of the toilets and eating places, they is inadequate compliance level to WASH programs at school, does not provide soap at all hand wash station, toilets are not working well, water not often available and the back tank is not enough.

Figure 1: shows student knowledge on WASH

Figure 1 above shows that 70.80%/n=170 of the respondents were knowledgeable about WASH compared to those that knew nothing on WASH represented by 29.20%/n=70. The results showed that school curriculum included education on hygiene as outlined through the responses given by

respondents (YES; 74.20%/n=178, NO; 25.80%/n=62). Knowledge on WASH to be a preventive route for diseases, response (YES; 72.50%/n=174, NO 27.50%/n=66).

Figure 2: Shows attitude to who is responsible for WASH at school

Figure 2 shows that the attitude of respondents toward who was responsible for cleaning the toilet demonstrated reviewed that Caretakers were responsible by the 77.5% n=186 response given while 6.3% n=15 of pupils said pupils, 6.3% n=15 were for Teachers and those who stated that everyone (All of the above 10% n=24).

Figure 3: shows attitude of students to WASH compliance.

From figure 3. According to the figure above the response to the question of who is responsible for personal hygiene of the pupils at your school (Mitanto secondary school)? The response were give as follows: (Pupils 52.5% n=126), (Teachers 21.7% n=52), (school administration; 25.8% n=62).

Figure 4: Shows practice influencing compliance level to WASH

The chart above demonstrates practices of school administration support in implementation of the activities.

Figure 5, 6: Shows practices on washing hands in line with the level of compliance toward WASH.

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 5 shows that the highest percentage 240 respondents interviewed (45.40% n=109) was for those who only practiced hand washing hygiene on washing hands after visiting the toilet while (27.90% n=67) washed hands before preparing food and the other (26.70% n=64) washed before eating. Figure 6 on the same frequency of (n=240), shows that the medium of washing hands by; water only (65% n=156), Water and Soap (35% n=84).

CHAPTER FIVE

5.1 DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

5.1.1 Introduction

This research has been designed for assessing the knowledge, attitude and practices influencing compliance to water, sanitation and hygiene (wash) among school Pupils at Mitanto secondary School of Kitwe District, and this will be discussed in this chapter Five (5) according to the findings that were done during the interviews.

5.1.2 Knowledge

According to the level of knowledge of pupils at Mitanto Secondary School in line with this research about Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH). Pupils gave a clear picture by the way they responded during the interviews that were conducted at the school.

From Chapter four on figure 1, the findings revealed that pupils were aware and possessed adequate knowledge about sanitation and hygiene noticed from the responses of 70.80% of n=170 of knowledge and about 29.20% of n=70 pupils were seen to have little knowledge on the WASH from (n=240) of pupils who were interviewed. And it is also noticed that from the school curriculum included education on hygiene is given in response by the respondents showing (74.20%/n=178), out of 240 of pupils who were interviewed.

Relating to disease prevention pupils showed to have knowledge of WASH preventing diseases, a high number of students gave response by (72.50%/n=174), out of pupils that were been interviewed. This gives a clear picture that pupils had full knowledge on water, sanitation and hygiene.

5.1.3 Attitude toward compliance levels to WASH

The negative attitude of pupils to WASH here is shown in the response extracted from the questionnaire showing it clear that their attitude was not favorable seen from “who is responsible of cleaning the toilet response,” and it was demonstrated that Pupils knew that only caretaker are

responsible in cleaning their toilets shown with 77.5% (n=186) of pupils response and only less percentage (10%) of 240 pupils showed the good attitude. And again we here see in **Figure 3.** on which 52.5% mentioned that it was the responsibility of pupils themselves for their personal hygiene at school and others gave the answer of teachers being responsible as well as school administration for the hygiene of the school which shows that there is still need for the pupils to change in their attitude toward WASH.

5. 1.4 Practices compliance level to WASH.

The study assessed the hygiene enabling school setting using structured observational questioning and checklist. The study suggests that the proportion of having hygiene enabling school has shown difference in the key hygiene behavior. From figure 4 the frequency of (n=240) we see here shows practices compliances to be 45.4% out of 240 pupils who were assessed demonstrated hand washing after visiting a toilet, and some few others of (27.9% n=67) practised hygiene before preparing food by and some pupils before eating. On Figure 5 it was seen that (65% n=156), water only was used without antiseptic solutions for the preventive sake.

This also shows that practicing of WASH by pupils and the school had not worked on those principles and this as contributed to the cause of so many diseases because of failing to practice WASH in schools in many schools.

5. 1. 5 Observation checklist

The study assessed by observation Checklist to help us out with the Knowledge, Attitude and Practices Influencing Compliance to Water, Sanitation And Hygiene (Wash) Among School Pupils at Mitanto Secondary School, and from **Table 5** observation checklist we observed that there was a low of practice WASH standard seen by the school consisting of 8 toilets for boys, 10 toilets for girls, the school does not provide hand washing facilities at the entrance/exit of the toilets and eating places, there was inadequate compliance to WASH programs at school, soap was also not provided at all hand wash station, toilets are not working well, water not often available and the back tank is not enough. This also tells us why the compliance toward WASH among the pupils was very low at school.

CHAPTER SIX

6.1 CONCLUSION

This study revealed that sanitation and hygiene practices at Mitanto Secondary School are remarkably poor due to supply-side responses. Despite the remarkable increase in the number of students who were knowledgeable about WASH, the promotion of improved sanitary and hygiene facilities has been overlooked at this school just from our observation and the response given by pupils from the interview. Therefore, a multi-level promotional intervention focusing on provider responses is needed to advance an enhanced, need-oriented, and effective sanitary and hygiene system that can promote improved hygiene and sanitary practices at the school for the benefits of the pupils and the school at large.

6.2 Recommendation to improve compliance on water hygiene and sanitation at the school

In line with the WHO guideline, World Health Organization recommends a pupil-toilet ratio of 1:30 boys and 1:25 toilets for girls (OCHA, 2014). And Mitanto Secondary School having 8 toilets for boys the all school is not enough and ten (10) toilets for girls is not also enough the school need to work on building more toilets to accommodate the all pupils. Consider gender perspectives in planning new infrastructure and construction

WASH-related materials and agents (i.e. supplying handwashing products, cleaning materials, washing equipment) should be regularly supplied to ensure quality cleaning services. A toilet cleaning checklist may be introduced to ensure quality cleaning services by cleaning professionals. WASH-related programs and key messages may be developed and displayed to promote good hygiene habits that remind the individual user to maintain good hygiene behavior. Regular monitoring and inspection of cleaning professionals and checking the toilet checklist to ensure quality services. Promote low-cost solutions such as soapy water or chlorine tablets/a tablet that has been proven effective in resource-limited settings should be introduced to minimize costs.

Pupils should be evaluated and be advised that it is their responsibility too not just the care taker for the hygiene of the school.

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QUESTIONNAIRE

Introduction to respondents

Title: Structured questionnaire on the knowledge, attitudes and practices influencing compliance levels to water, sanitation and hygiene.

Questionnaire number

Date

Dear respondent,

Your school has been chosen to help answer this questionnaire which is strictly for academic purpose. The exercise serves to uphold your right of confidentiality.

Instructions: Answer all the questions below.

Section A: Socio-demography

1. Gender

Female

Male

2. Age

a. 11-13 years

b. 14-16 years

c. 17 and above

3. Grade of pupil

Grade 8 & 9

Grade 10 & 11

Grade 12

Section B- Knowledge

4. Do you have knowledge on the importance of WASH in schools?
- a. Yes
 - b. No
5. Can WASH prevent you from contracting diseases?
- a. Yes
 - b. No
6. Where do you normally receive information on water, sanitation and hygiene? (SHADE ALL THAT APPLY)
- a) Posters and handbills
 - b) Health education by community health workers
 - c) Health education by teachers
 - d) Health education by school administration
 - e) Health education by Sanitation Action Group in school
 - f) None of the above
7. Does the school curriculum include education on hygiene?
- Yes
- No
8. What do you think is the harm or danger of not treating water to drink or not storing drinking water safely?
- g) Diarrhea
 - h) Cholera
 - i) Typhoid
 - j) Acute respiratory infection
 - k) Water will be contaminated
 - l) Sickness (unspecified)

Section C: Attitude

9. Who is responsible of cleaning the toilet?
- e) Pupils

- f) Teachers
- g) Caretakers
- h) All of the above

10. How often do you participate in WASH activities?

- a. Often
- b. Fairly often
- c. Not

11. Who is responsible for personal hygiene of the pupils at your school?

- a. Pupils
- b. Teachers
- c. School administration

12. Do you wash hands with soap after toilet use?

Yes

No

13. Do you think diarrheal diseases are caused by poor hygiene?

Yes

No

Section D: Practices

14. When do you wash hands?

- a. After visiting the toilet
- b. Before preparing food
- c. Before eating

15. How does the school administration support in implementation of the activities?

- e) Providing money
- f) Providing materials
- g) Allocating time for activities
- h) Monitoring

16. What is the medium of washing hands?

- d) Water only
- e) Water and soap

f) Water and ash

17. What WASH activities do you have at your school?

- a. Hand wash maintenance []
- b. Maintenance of latrines []
- c. Hygiene education []
- d. Environmental education []
- e. Provision of safe drinking water []
- f. Others (kindly explain) []

18. How many hand wash facilities does your school have?(tick all that apply)

- a. Concrete tank with tap []
- b. Bucket with cup []
- c. Plastic containers with tap []
- d. Plastic containers without tap []

OBSERVATIONAL CHECKLIST

19. How many toilets or pit latrines does the school have for girls?

- a. 10 -13
- b. 14-16
- c. 17-20

20. How many toilets or pit latrines does the school have for boys?

- a. 10 -13
- b. 14-16
- c. 17-20

21. Does the school provide hand washing facilities at every entrance/exit of the toilet and eating places?

- a. Yes
- b. No

22. How adequate is the compliance levels to WASH program at your school?

- a. Adequate
- b. Inadequate

23. Is soap available at all handwashing stations?

- a. Yes

- b. No
24. Is there a backup water tank?
- a. Yes
 - b. No
25. Are waste disposal bins available?
- a. Yes
 - b. No
26. What is the condition of the toilets?
- a. Working well
 - b. Not working well
27. How often is water available?
- a. Throughout the day
 - b. Only for few hours in a day.
 - c. Never available.

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Introduction

Hello my name is Nchimunya Mweete from Rusangu University and I am carrying out research on the knowledge, attitudes and practices influencing compliance levels to water, sanitation, and hygiene among pupils at Mitanto High School.

Purpose of Study

To find out the prevailing knowledge, attitudes and practices influencing compliance levels to water, sanitation, and hygiene among pupils at Mitanto High School.

Study Procedures

This study will involve using a questionnaire and observation checklist. Participants will be chosen through simple random sampling and where question is not understood, they will be clarified.

Confidentiality

The participants and their answers to the questions will be kept confidential and will only be used for research purposes.

Study Benefits

The results obtained from this study will assist with evaluating whether more needs to be done with compliance to WASH and what changes can be made to the current WASH interventions, The findings may also provide information on recommendations for policy-makers, educators and public health officers as they plan, implement and promote their advocacy on water, sanitation and hygiene in schools.

Study Risks

There are no health risks associated with participating in this study.